

Research Article

Growth and fruit yield of garden egg (*Solanum gilo*) as affected by different organic fertilizer types and rates

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Abstract

Field trials were conducted during the growing seasons of 2016 and 2017 at the Experimental farm of National Horticultural Research Institute Mbato out-Station Okigwe Imo State, Nigeria to investigate the effect of different organic fertilizer types and rates on production of garden egg (*Solanum gilo*).The treatments were three organic fertilizer types (Poultry manure, *Tithonia diversifolia* leaves and *Moringa oleifera* leaves) and three application rates of 0 tonnes/ha (control), 10 tonnes/ha and 20 tonnes/ha. The experiment was laid out as a 3 x 3 factorial in Randomized Complete Block Design replicated four times. Each plot size measured 3 m x 3 m. Garden egg seedlings were transplanted at spacing of 1 m x 1 m apart. The manure types were incorporated into the soil two weeks before transplanting the garden egg seedlings. Data were collected on growth parameters such as plant height (cm), canopy spread (cm), number of leaves and stem girth (cm) at 4 and 8 weeks after transplanting (WAT). Also, number of fruits and fruit weight were determined. All data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and means were separated using fishers LSD at 5% probability level. The result of the trial shows that poultry manure gave the highest mean number of leaves value at both 4 and 8 WAT with values of 43 and 53 respectively. This was followed by *Moringa oleifera* with *Tithonia diversifolia* recoding the least number of leaves. However, application of 20 t/ha recorded the highest mean number of leaves values of 39 and 46 at 4 WAT and 8 WAT respectively. The interactions of the fertilizer types and rates on a number of leaves were significant. A similar trend of results was also recorded on the effect of different fertilizer types and rates on the canopy spread of garden egg. Poultry manure showed highest mean values of 38 cm and 41 cm at 4 WAT and 8 WAT respectively, with 20 t/ha rate of application also recording highest means. The number of fruits was highest in plots treated with poultry manure with 97 followed

by *M.oleifera* (96). There were significant interactions between the fertilizer types and rates on a number

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of fruits. Similarly, the fruit weight followed the same trend with number of fruits with poultry manure plots having highest fruit weight than *M.oleifera* and *T. diversifolia* plots. Highest mean fruit weight of 2.56 t/ha was recorded in poultry manure plot, followed by 2.49 t/ha in *M.oleifera* plots. In terms of soil amendment using these fertilizer types, poultry manure is recommended at 20 t/ha based on its outstanding performance.

Key words; Fertilizer types, garden egg, growth and yield, rates

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Introduction

Garden egg (*Solanum gilo*) is a native of India (Yayock *et al.*, 1998, Messien, 1992). In West Africa, they are more popularly grown for fruit and in some cases for their leaves and tender roots (Opara and Asiegbu, 1996). The Ultisol which constitutes the main agricultural lands of South Eastern Nigeria covers more than 70% of the total land area (Mbagwu, 1992). The soils of this part of Nigeria suffers the constraints of low reserves of essential plant nutrients and high soil acidity (Mbagwu, 1992).The use of organic manure is recommended for managing such soils to improve the nutrient content and other soil physical characteristics (Mbagwu and Ekweala, 1990). Garden egg production in Nigeria is on the increase and the quest for its increased production is often constrained by low nutrient status of our soils. The recognition of the high nutritive values of this crop made it one of the crops in demand in the market year round.

Nutrient elements have been established to be important in garden egg cultivation (Olaniyan and Nwachukwu, 2003). While nitrogen is important in vegetative development, phosphorus is needed to stimulate flowering and fruit formation while potassium is for seed setting. The high cost and scarcity of inorganic fertilizers in developing countries prohibit their use by most peasant farmers, there by generating renewed interest in the use of organic materials as nutrient sources for the cultivation of nutrient demanding crops like garden egg (Saidu *et al.*, 2010). Organic fertilizers supply organic matter to the soil that modifies soils physical and chemical properties (Onwuka *et al.*, 2008). They are slow release nutrient sources that make nutrients available for longer period of time (Omotayo and Chukwuka, 2009).

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Poultry manure and other green manures are commonly available organic material source in Southeast Nigeria. Green manure which includes *Tithonia diversifolia* and *Moringa oleifera* are becoming a common site in this part of the country and their

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leaves are known to have fertilizing effects on the soil, hence the attempt to use it as organic source for soil amendment in the ultisols of Mbato Okigwe zone with characteristic low reserve of essential plant nutrients and high soil acidity. There is a gap in published information with respect to manuring of *Solanum* using *Tithonia diversifolia* and *Moringa oleifera*. That is what informed this trial with the objectives to determine the organic fertilizer type and rate that will give the best performance and make recommendations to farmers.

Materials and Methods

This trial was conducted at National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT) Mbato out station, Okigwe, Imo State, Nigeria during the 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons to evaluate the effect of some organic soil amendments and rates on the growth and yield of garden egg (*Solanum gilo* var Ngwa large). The station lies between Latitude 05°33' N and Longitude 07° and 23' E and 130 meters above sea level. The area enjoys over 2,200 mm of mean annual rainfall with temperature range of between 21° C and 32° C. Prepared field was marked out using pegs into plots of 3 m x 3 m dimensions. Pre-planting soil samples were collected from a depth of 0 - 30 cm using soil sampling auger. The soil samples were processed and analyzed to determine the physical and chemical properties of the soil. The organic fertilizer types were also analyzed. The site was well drained, non-gravelly soil. The soil texture was sandy loam (743 g/kg sand, 155 g/kg silt, 102 g/kg clay) characterized by low N value (0.90 gkg⁻¹), low P value (6.80 mgkg⁻¹) and low K value (0.19 cmolkg⁻¹) with soil pH of 4.58, which is very acidic. Poultry manure, *Tithonia diversifolia* leaves and *Moringa oleifera* leaves each at 0 tonnes/ha (control), 10 tonnes/ha and 20 tonnes/ha forms the treatments. The poultry manure, *Tithonia diversifolia* leaves and *Moringa oleifera* leaves were placed at a depth of 30 cm on the planting spots two weeks before transplanting. With a spacing of 1 m x 1 m, a total of 16 plants /plot and 10,000 plants /ha of garden egg seedlings previously raised in the nursery were transplanted. The trial was laid out as a 3 x 3 factorial in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Supplies of seedlings were done at two weeks after transplanting. Growth parameters such as plant height (cm), canopy spread (cm), number of leaves and stem girth (cm) were taken bi-weekly at 4 and 8 weeks after transplanting. Yield and yield components such as number of fruits and fruit weight were determined.

Soil Analysis

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The soil samples collected from the field were air dried; sieved using a 2 mm mesh sized sieve and then subjected to routine laboratory analysis. The particle size distribution was determined by hydrometer method according to the procedure of

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Gee and Or (2002). Sodium hexametaphosphate was used as dispersant. The soil pH was determined in 1:1 soil water ratio suspension using EEL glass electrode pH meter. Organic carbon was determined using chromic wet oxidation method and total soil nitrogen was determined by the Kjeldahl digestion method. Available phosphorus was determined on Bray -1 extractant method. Exchangeable K^+ , and Na^+ were extracted using 1N ammonium acetate (NH_4OAC) and then determined using flame photometer. Exchangeable Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} were determined using ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA). Exchangeable acidity was measured titrimetrically using 1N KCl against 0.05N sodium hydroxide. Effective cation exchange capacity was calculated from the summation of all exchangeable bases and total exchangeable acidity. Percentage base saturation (PBS) was calculated by the summation of total exchangeable bases divided by effective cation exchange capacity and then multiplied by 100.

Organic Manure Analysis

The nutrients were extracted by dry ashing method. Air dried ground manure samples were sieved through a 2mm sieve and ignited at $450^{\circ}C$ for 2 hours. The ash was extracted with HCl. Organic matter (OM) was determined by Walkley - Black dichromate digestion methods and total nitrogen was determined by the Kjeldahl method. The P was determined by ammonium Molybdate/ ammonium vanadate blue method. Potassium was determined using the flame photometer and Ca and Mg by EDTA titration. The pH in 0.01M $CaCl_2$ was determined using a glass electrode pH meter. All data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and means were separated using fishers LSD at 5% probability level.

Results and Discussion

Soil Properties Used for the Study

Some properties of the soil used for the trial indicates that the soil is acidic in reaction with pH values in 1:1 soil-water ratio of 4.58. Based on FAO guidelines (2002) for interpretation of soil analysis, the soil organic carbon (SOC) content was low, with values of 1.60 g/kg. The total nitrogen content was generally low, with values of 0.90 g/kg. The total nitrogen content followed the same trend as SOC content. The available phosphorus content (mg/kg) of the soil was low, with values of 6.80. Exchangeable cations (calcium, magnesium, potassium and sodium) contents were low, with calcium and magnesium dominating the exchange complex. Calcium content was 3.20 cmol/kg. Magnesium content was 1.60 cmol/kg, potassium was

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0.19 cmol/kg, while sodium content was 0.06 cmol/kg. Effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC) value was also low, with value of 5.75 cmol/kg. The texture of the soil showed that the soil is sandy loam (Table 1).

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The low SOC content could be attributed to the inherent characteristics of the soil and climatic conditions which result to the high rate of organic matter decomposition associated with the tropical agricultural production systems. Arable soils of Southeastern Nigeria are mostly sandy, acidic ultisols with low organic matter and nutrient status (Nottidge *et al.*, 2005, 2007). These soil conditions are also dominant in the rainforest zones of the humid tropics (Nottidge *et al.*, 2005). The low nitrogen content could be attributed to a number of factors such as the high rate of SOM decomposition as a result of rainfall and temperature conditions as well as high leaching and microbial activities prevalent in the tropics.

Table 1: Some physical and chemical properties of the soil used for the experiment

Soil Properties	Values
pH(H ₂ O)	4.58
Organic carbon (g/kg)	1.60
Total N (g/kg)	0.90
Available P(mg/kg)	6.80
Ca (cmol/kg)	3.20
Mg (cmol/kg)	1.60
K (cmol/kg)	0.19
Na (cmol/kg)	0.06
ECEC (cmol/kg)	5.75
Base saturation (%)	58.2
C/N ratio	11:54
Sand (g/kg)	743
Silt (g/kg)	155
Clay (g/kg)	102
Exchangeable Mn (cmol/kg)	1.08
Exchangeable Zn (cmol/kg)	1.70
Exchangeable Fe (cmol/kg)	6.23
Exchangeable Cu (cmol/kg)	18.75

Chemical Properties of the Organic Material Used for the Study

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As shown in Table 2, nitrogen content was highest (15g/kg) in poultry manure and lowest (11.1 g/kg) in *T.diversifolia* . Calcium content was highest (30.5 mg/kg) in poultry manure and lowest (21.5 mg/kg) in *T.diversifolia*. Magnesium was highest

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(9.6 mg/kg) in *M.oleifera* and lowest (6.0 mg/kg) in *T.diversifolia* . Potassium was highest (29.3 mg/kg) in poultry manure and lowest (20.3 mg/kg) in *T.diversifolia* , Among the three organic manure sources, poultry manure seems to be the best in terms of nutrient composition when compared with the other organic manure sources.

Table 2: Some properties of the organic manures used for the experiment

Properties	Poultry manure	<i>T. diversifolia</i>	<i>M.oleifera</i>
Organic carbon (%)	14.9	17.8	17.3
Total N (g/kg)	15.0	11.1	12.4
Available P(mg/kg)	34.6	10.4	16.0
Ca(mg/kg)	30.5	21.5	28.0
Mg(mg/kg)	7.6	6.0	9.6
K(mg/kg)	29.3	20.3	25.0
Na(mg/kg)	4.2	8.6	4.4
Exchangeable (mg/kg)	Mn 66.3	58.7	59
Exchangeable (mg/kg)	Zn 5.4	129	39
Exchangeable (mg/kg)	Fe 7.6	6.7	6.0
Exchangeable (mg/kg)	Cu 1.7	29.5	13.7

The effect of different fertilizer types and rates on the number of leaves of garden egg at 4 weeks and 8 weeks after transplanting (WAT) is shown in Table 3. Poultry manure gave highest mean values at both 4 and 8 WAT with values of 43 and 53 respectively. This was followed by *Moringa oleifera* with *Tithonia diversifolia* recording the least number of leaves. However, application of 20 t/ha recorded the highest mean values of 39 and 46 at 4 WAT and 8 WAT respectively. The interaction of the fertilizer types and rates on the number of leaves was significant. The high increase in the number of leaves of garden egg in plots treated with poultry manure indicates that the manure was able to release enough nutrients for the growth of garden egg. John *et al*, (2004) reported that poultry manure contains essential nutrient elements

associated with high photosynthetic activities and thus promotes root and vegetative growth. Also, Onyegbule *et al*; 2016 recorded significant increase in number of leaves of *Solanum gilo* using poultry manure amendment.

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Table 3. Effect of different fertilizer types and rates on number of leaves of garden egg at 4 and 8 WAT in 2016 and 2017

Fertilizer types	Rates of application								
	4wks				8wks				
	0 t/ha	10 t/ha	20 t/ha	Mean	0 t/ha	10 t/ha	20 t/ha	Mean	
<i>M. oleifera</i>	34	42	45	40	50	53	50	51	
Poultry manure	43	43	45	43	51	55	52	53	
<i>T. diversifolia</i>	28	24	27	26	32	27	31	30	
Mean	35	36	39		44	45	46		
LSD(0.05) Fertilizer type -18.28				LSD(0.05) Fertilizer type - 19.98					
LSD(0.05) Rate of application -18.28				LSD(0.05) Rate of application - 21.54					
LSD(0.05) FxR - 31.67				LSD (0.05) FxR - 38.59					

Similar trend of results were recorded on the effect of different fertilizer types and rates on canopy spread of garden egg. Poultry manure showed highest mean values of 37.83 cm and 41.43 cm at 4 WAT and 8 WAT respectively, with 20 t/ha rate of application also recording highest means (Table 4). The high nutrient release by the poultry manure improved soil properties and hence, the canopy covers. There were no significant differences ($p>0.05$) in the treatment means between poultry manure and *T. diversifolia* at 0 t/ha and 10 t/ha at both 4 and 6 WAT, but *T. diversifolia* recorded the least mean values across the weeks. Application rate of 20 t/ha of poultry manure for garden egg production in Mbato Okigwe zone confirms the earlier findings of Onyegbule and Asawalam, 2015.

Table 4 Effect of different fertilizer types and rates on canopy spread of garden egg at 4 and 8 WAT in 2016 and 2017

Fertilizer type	Rates of application								
	4 wks				8 wks				
	0 t/ha	10 t/ha	20t/ha	Mean	0t/ha	10t/ha	20t/ha	Mean	
<i>M. oleifera</i>	27.6	32.5	44.3	35.13	30.6	35.8	49.4	38.60	
Poultry manure	32.3	36.5	45.7	37.83	36.4	40.1	47.8	41.43	
<i>T. diversifolia</i>	33.2	33.5	26.7	31.13	38.5	38.2	29.7	35.46	
Mean	31.03	34.16	38.9		35.16	38.03	42.30		
LSD(0.05) Fertilizer type - 6.98				LSD(0.05) Fertilizer type - 7.22					

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LSD(0.05) Rate of application - **6.98**
7.23
 LSD(0.05) FxR - **12.10**

LSD(0.05) Rate of application -
 LSD (0.05) FxR - **14.20**

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The effect of the different fertilizer types and rates on plant height of garden egg was favoured by *Moringa oleifera* than the other fertilizer types (Table 5). The interaction of the fertilizer types and rates at both 4 and 8 WAT was significant. 20 t/ha rate of application showed highest mean values.

Table 5. Effect of different fertilizer types and rates on plant height of garden egg at 4 and 8 WAT in 2016 and 2017

Fertilizer type	Rates of application								
	4 wks				8 wks				
	0 t/ha	10 t/ha	20 t/ha	Mean	0 t/ha	10 t/ha	20 t/ha	Mean	
<i>M. oleifera</i>	27.2	30.8	48.9	35.63	33.2	37.4	53.5	41.37	
Poultry manure	23.4	30.4	42.8	32.20	26.8	34.5	46.8	36.03	
<i>T. diversifolia</i>	28.1	29.9	21.3	26.43	32.5	31.5	25.4	29.80	
Mean	26.23	30.37	37.67		30.83	34.47	41.9		
LSD(0.05) Fertilizer type - 8.80				LSD(0.05) Fertilizer type - 10.14					
LSD(0.05) Rate of application - 8.80				LSD(0.05) Rate of application - 10.14					
LSD(0.05) FxR - 15.25				LSD (0.05) FxR - 17.23					

However, Poultry manure showed the highest mean stem girth values of 0.86 cm and 1.0 cm respectively with 20 t/ha rate recording the highest mean values (Table 6). This was followed by *M.oleifera* with *T.diversifolia* giving the least mean stem girth values. The manure application was able to increase the vegetative growth of garden egg. It was earlier reported by Aliyu (2010) that poultry manure has profound effect on the vegetative development of garden egg and it ensures healthy and vigorous growth of the crop.

Table 6. Effect of different fertilizer types and rates on stem girth of garden egg at 4 and 8 WAT in 2016 and 2017

Fertilizer type	Rates of application							
	4 wks				8 wks			
	0 t/ha	10 t/ha	20t/ha	Mean	0 t/ha	10t/ha	20 t/ha	Mean
<i>M. oleifera</i>	0.6	0.73	1.05	0.79	0.7	0.82	1.2	0.90
Poultry manure	0.72	0.77	1.10	0.86	0.81	0.95	1.25	1.00
<i>T. diversifolia</i>	0.6	0.72	0.56	0.62	0.7	0.82	0.72	0.74
Mean	0.64	0.74	0.90		0.73	0.86	1.05	

LSD(0.05) Fertilizer type - **0.178**

LSD(0.05) Fertilizer type - **0.25**

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LSD(0.05) Rate of application – **0.178**
 LSD(0.05) FxR – **0.31**

LSD(0.05) Rate of application – **0.25**
 LSD (0.05) FxR – **0.52**

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The yield of garden egg as influenced by the application of different fertilizer types and rates is shown on Table 7. The number of fruits was highest in plots treated with poultry manure with 96.9 followed by *M.oleifera* (96). There were significant interaction between the fertilizer types and rates on number of fruits. Similarly, the fruit weight followed the same trend with number of fruits with poultry manure plots having highest fruit weight than *M.oleifera* and *T.diversifolia* plots. Highest mean fruit weight of 2.56 t/ha was recorded in poultry manure plot, followed by 2.49 t/ha in *M.oleifera* plots. The better performance in fruit yield of garden egg in plots treated with poultry manure may be due to the release of more nutrients from the soil. Dauda et al, (2008) reported that poultry manure promotes vigorous growth, increase meristematic and physiological activities in the plant due to supply of plant nutrient and improvement in soil properties. These often result in the synthesis of more photo assimilates which are used in producing fruits.

Table 7. Effect of different fertilizer types and rates on yield of garden egg at 4 and 8 WAT in 2016 and 2017

Fertilizer type	Rates of application								
	No of fruits /plot				Fruit wt (t/ha)				
	0 t/ha	10 t/ha	20t/ha	Mean	0 t/ha	10 t/ha	20 t/ha	Mean	
<i>M. oleifera</i>	82	99	106	96	2.06	2.63	2.78	2.49	
Poultry manure	84	92	115	97	2.00	2.31	3.36	2.56	
<i>T. diversifolia</i>	80	82	85	82	1.96	2.02	2.25	2.08	
Mean	82	91	102		2.01	2.32	2.80		
LSD(0.05) Fertilizer type - 2.63				LSD(0.05) Fertilizer type - 0.68					
LSD(0.05) Rate of application - 4.43				LSD(0.05) Rate of application - 0.69					
LSD(0.05) FxR - 6.33				LSD (0.05) FxR - 1.69					

Conclusion

The different fertilizer types studied was able to improve the growth yield of garden egg. The result of the trial shows that poultry manure gave the highest mean number of leaves value at both 4 and 8 WAT with values of 43 and 53 respectively. This was followed by *Moringa oleifera* with *Tithonia diversifolia* recording the least number of leaves. However, application of 20 t/ha recorded the highest mean number of leaves values of 39 and 46 at 4 WAT and 8 WAT respectively. The interaction of the fertilizer types and rates on number of leaves was significant. The number of fruits was highest in plots treated with poultry manure with 97 followed by *M.oleifera* (96). There were significant interaction between the fertilizer types and rates on number

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of fruits. Similarly, the fruit weight followed the same trend as number of fruits, with poultry manure plots having highest fruit weight than *M.oleifera* and *T. diversifolia* plots. Highest mean fruit weight of 2.56 t/ha was recorded in poultry

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manure plot, followed by 2.49 t/ha in *M.oleifera* plots. In terms of soil amendment using these fertilizer types, poultry manure is recommended at 20 t/ha based on its outstanding performance.

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